

Studies in the Acenaphthenequinone Series. Part II.

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The present investigation is a continuation of the work of Sircar and Sen (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8 605) and undertaken with the object of establishing the formation of iminazoles from oxazoles, contrary to the work of Japp and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1882, 41, 146).

Sircar and Sen (*loc. cit.*) have prepared both oxazoles and iminazoles from acenaphthenequinone in presence of ammonia with the same aldehyde under different experimental conditions; at the temperature of melting ice only oxazoles are formed while at higher temperature only iminazoles are formed. Again some of the aldehydes yielded a mixture of oxazole and iminazole at the temperature of melting ice.

The formation of both oxazoles and iminazoles by the condensation of the same aldehyde with acenaphthenequinone in presence of ammonia naturally leads one to suppose that probably in these reactions oxazoles are first formed which by subsequent replacement of the oxygen atom of the ring by the NH-group forms iminazoles. Ruhemann (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 75, 713) and Meyer and Oppelt (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 3376) have actually been able to replace the oxygen atom by NH-group in pyrone and allied compounds. In order to justify the above supposition Sircar and Sen (*loc. cit.*) have shown that when an oxazole is heated with ammonia in a sealed tube under pressure, the percentage of nitrogen in the resulting product appreciably increased though the corresponding iminazole could not be isolated.

The authors have now been able to prepare 4'-acetylamino-2-phenylacenaphthiminazole (I, R = NH) from 4'-acetylamino-2-phenylacena-
thoxazole (I, R = O).

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Acenaphthenequinone (1 g.) was thoroughly mixed with a little more than the molecular proportion of *p*-acetylaminobenzaldehyde, dissolved in boiling amyl alcohol, and dry ammonia gas was passed through the hot solution for about 4 minutes. When the reaction had just started, the mixture was cooled in a freezing mixture and ammonia gas was passed for 2 hours. A portion of it was allowed to stand overnight for the preparation of oxazoles and this oxazole had the same properties as described by Sircar and Sen (*loc. cit.*). (Found : N, 8.81. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{14}O_2N_2$: N, 8.59 per cent). The solution left in the flask, was boiled and ammonia gas was passed through it for a further period of 2 hours and the solution left overnight. The separated red precipitate was washed with ether, crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and benzene as yellow microcrystalline powder, melting at 250° (decomp.) and had the properties of the iminazole as shown in our previous work. (Found : N, 12.60. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{15}ON_3$: N, 12.92 per cent). Similar results were, however, not obtained with other aldehydes.

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